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**CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES AND
FUTURISTIC APPROACHES
FOR CREATING SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY**

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Digitising Women Safety: A Game of Phones!

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Abstract—A major aim of this article is to synthesize various conceptual frameworks, research findings and practice-based knowledge on collaboration into an integrative model meant to design interventions for people suffering from a social problem. These interventions focus on making such individuals collaborate to shape social action in the direction of positive social change. In our research, we first use the model to explicate the problems being faced by female commuters in Delhi who frequently use the public transport. Our sample consisted of adolescent girls and working women (N= 750) who were surveyed about the: (i) levels of stress and anxiety experienced when traveling, (ii) history of harassment faced, and (iii) their specific travel behavior patterns. On the basis of the output generated from the preliminary survey, an intervention in the form of an android mobile application was proposed to enable these women to act in collaboration by means of traveling together. Finally, the results obtained after computing the Mc Nemar's Change Test for binary-matched data on a one sample pre-test-post-test research design, indicated the app as being effective in getting women to take responsibility for each other's safety.

Keywords: Civic Collaboration, Group Cohesion, Social Action, Social Change

BACKGROUND OF THE RESEARCH

In our part of the world, when earth begins to cast its shadow, time is measured not by the ticking of a clock, but by the frantic heartbeats of distressed people as they wait for their mothers and wives; and daughters and sisters to return-fearing the worst in the advent of increased threat to their safety-the instances of which routinely feature in the morning newspapers.

With crimes against the fair sex becoming increasingly ubiquitous in the national capital of India, a surge in the instances of violence and harassment directed towards women is not unprecedented. In fact, recent studies have shown women as being the most vulnerable using public transports and transits in Delhi (Crime Records Bureau, 2014; Jagori, 2010a, 2010b, 2011). It is unfortunate that even after the implementation of several measures like increased formal surveillance, establishment of fast track courts promising timely justice, and the like, the safety of women in the city continues to be jeopardized.

It is rather alarming that despite recognizing the gravity of the situation and the pressing need to act, the issue of lack of women's safety fails to attract much scholarly attention. Moreover, a dearth of action research in this field threatens to render other investigations aimed at understanding the specific characteristics of potential crime zones, or the impact of traumatic experiences of victimization on women's psychological health, as mere data collection exercises. Thus, this research is an endeavour to explore the role social psychologists can play in the initiation of social action to expand the roots of social psychology beyond the individual level of analysis towards macro-level ones that could initiate (and not merely explain) social change.

Given this context, with 'collaborative behaviour' coming to the forefront of psychological research by means of extensive theoretical and empirical investigations in several setups like organizations, education and now even IT, the literature on collaboration is sure to provide some interesting insights about the structures promising its effectiveness, factors leading to its inhibition or facilitation, and also its implications on a multitude of individual variables. However, as a phenomenon, collaboration does not have to occur only in such complex contexts. Even in the normal course of our lives, we come across many individuals around us who engage in solving problems that affect the community at large. Since battling for change is not an individual fight and requires the collective efforts of all the like-minded